

Regeneration of Place Identity in Urban Space (Case Study: Baharestan Square in Iran)

Bahareh Heydari¹

¹PhD in Urban Design, TU Dortmund, Fakultät Raumplanung, Fachgebiet Stä

Abstract: The physical structure of the Iranian cities has been changed in Islamic era. Square and street are two important spatial elements of Islamic cities. Square, has been religious (e.g., Mosques) and economical (e.g., the markets) roles. Also, it has been as a common place around which governmental buildings were constructed, gained momentum. Thus, Squares are memorized place for residents. This research has been studied Baharestan square in Iran as historical urban space. The aim of this paper is, achieving to identity in value urban spaces. This research is applied and the research method is "descriptive-analytical". In order to data collected was used questionnaire tool. So, in order to analyzing data was used SPSS software and SWOT technique.

Keyword: Regeneration, place identity, Baharestan square

Introduction

Urban public places have long played an important role in the life of nations. As stages for rituals, locations of national monuments, or sites of protest or resistance, they have helped to construct, reproduce or transform narratives of national identity (Sumartojo, 2012, 67). A brief look at the history of the evolution of the ancient cities of Iran into the modern ones shows that square has gradually gained significance amongst the body of urban elements and has largely influenced the formation and organization of urban spaces in various periods. With man's presence and with a specific purpose in relation with the movement of the crowd, square, as an urban element, comes to existence and demonstrates bright views of a social centre. In Iran, since the ancient times up until when urbanization still has not left behind its original values for the modern functions, square along with other major urban elements in cities, especially the cities after Islam, played an important role in urban life of Iranian cities.; square in the Saljooqi era began to stabilize its position, gained conceptual and practical significance in the Safavi era, and reached its heyday in the Ghajari era. But it gradually faded into insignificance so that in the middle years of the Pahlavi era completely lost its popularity and in the recent two decades is an absolutely pending situation (Habibi, 2003. pp, 53-58).

Our past urban spaces enjoyed specific independence, character and identity, notions used for defining more general concepts like the sense of belonging and citizenship. Whereas the notion of urban space today reminds one of a collection of tall buildings, streets, offices, and parks, urban space is in fact a place where people interact and have a sense of citizenship. In other words, what makes a city is not a collection of physical establishments; rather people with their individual characteristics create the sense of identity and citizenship. The process of creating a sense of identity in an urban space is generally contingent on the opportunities and capacities of the setting, thereby acting as urban signs and symbols to promote the identity of the urban spaces.

The Square's symbolic role as a site of national history, its ongoing use for both the quotidian and the spectacular, as well as its location at the centre of a larger 'landscape of power' that takes in government, finance and cultural institutions, make it a unique subject for studying the means by which national identity is discussed, imagined and reproduced, and how different histories are either commemorated or forgotten (Sumartojo, 2012, 70). Baharestan Square is no exception in this regard; it is a historic-political site that has lost its social life and same as the other squares in Tehran has taken on a pragmatic traffic-related function. The square has a very important historical background and is considered to be one of

This article is published under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License 4.0

Author(s) retain the copyright of this article. Publication rights with Alkhaer Publications.

Published at: <http://www.ijsciences.com/pub/issue/2016-05/>

DOI: 10.18483/ijSci.1015; Online ISSN: 2305-3925; Print ISSN: 2410-4477

Bahareh Heydari (Correspondence)

bheydari2010@gmail.com

+

the most important poles of Tehran evidenced by the events occurred in the square in the last two centuries. Considering the high significance attached to the square with its structural, functional, and political features, this Article seeks to establish the features which can help recreate the identities of the historical squares in Iran. The Article has been organized into three sections. In the first section, we investigated the theoretical background of place identity, along with an evolutionary overview of the concept of square in Islamic cities are extensively reviewed; then, various aspects of Baharestan Square are discussed based on the relevant literature, and survey data obtained are investigated; finally, the factors and criteria which influence the recreation of the identity of the square along with the mainly structural instances are presented and, some strategies and designing policies are proposed to be employed in promoting the place identity of Iranian squares such as Baharestan square.

The present work seeks to find the factors which are influential in recreating the place identity of the historical squares of Iran, as the main objective of the study. Accordingly, optimal strategies to be useful in promoting the factors affecting the identity of Baharestan Square are proposed. To this purpose, the operational objectives of the study are stated as follows:

1. Developing optimal strategies for the preservation, promotion, and creation of the element contributing to the identity of this Square, as a historical and cultural place.
2. Investigating the notion and role of square in Islamic cities, with a focus on the historical and cultural identity.
3. Investigating the signs, elements and factors influencing the identity expressed by the square.
4. Specifying and developing the factors which give the square a sense of identity in the context of the national and historical events.

Research Methodology

The methodology of this study is descriptive – analytic and collecting data is done by documents-library and field. The data are generally gathered from scientific centre libraries like universities, organizations, institutes and research centers such as management and planning organization and internet, official statistics and censuses, urban development plans by consulting engineers, field study and so on. Also, was used from questioner tool. In order to analyzing data, was used SPSS software and SWOT technique.

This research attempt that answer some questions . Thus the hypotheses are:

- The building of the congress and the

historical body of the square has a pivotal role in recreating the place identity of Baharestan Square (Historic-political factors).

- Creating place identity in Baharestan Square has an important impact on promoting social participation, the sense of inviting, and establishing democracy in the square (Socio-cultural).
- The physical-functional indexes of Baharestan Square including the pedestrian –oriented, the historical body and especially the constituent components, signs and symbols of the square (the Parliament building, Masoodie complex, Negarestan Garden, Sepahsalar complex, the statue of Modarres etc.) play important parts in recreating the place identity of the square (Structural-Functional).
- Constructing elements related to historical events can contribute to the place identity of Baharestan Square and connect people to the past events (Historic-political).

Literature review

Identity is one of the most important issues in developing countries and especially in the current age of globalization. Numerous definitions have been given for the notion of identity but the dictionaries define it as the truth of a thing or person which includes his natural characteristics; personality, nature, existence, being etc. In the present section, the concepts of identity and place identity are briefly reviewed. Hence the current work focuses on identity factors in Islamic squares, only the identity factors from the viewpoint of theoreticians and the history of the evolution of square in Iran, highlighting aspects related to identity, are investigated.

In Webster Encyclopedia (Webster, 1988:597) four definitions are given for identity

- sameness of essential or generic character in different instances; sameness in all that constitutes the objective reality of a thing : oneness
- the distinguishing character or personality of an individual : individuality; the relation established by psychological identification
- the condition of being the same with something described or asserted
- an equation that is satisfied for all values of the symbols

In the present study, identity concerns a concept which gives a distinct character to a physical space.

Place identity

Place identity refers to a cluster of ideas about place and identity in the fields of geography, urban planning, urban design, landscape architecture,

environmental psychology, and urban sociology/ecological sociology. It concerns the meaning and significance of places for their inhabitants and users.

Identity is neither an easily reducible, nor a separable quality of places, it is neither constant nor absolute, nor is it constantly changing and variable. Identity is the glue which binds people together and connects them to place (Shafik and Aly, 2011, 505). Place identity is defined as a way through which any place communicates its own identity by means of the place of an individual or a group (Belinda Yuen, 2005:201; Proshansky, Fabian & Kaminoff, 1995). Place identity is a fundamental aspect that contributes to shape the identity of communities (Shafik and Aly, 2011, 503). Some places possess such a strong sense of identity that they give the same sense to different people. Place identity has a significant impact on the mental and emotional health of people and moderates the relationship between people and their environment (Belinda Yuen, 2005:201; Lowenthal, 1985; Lynch, 1972; Proshansky: Fabian and Kaminoff, 1983). Places have a pivotal role in the development and preservation of the group identity of people (Davenport & Anderson, 2005). They are thus important elements in the preservation and promotion of collective identity, bring peace and composure, and improve people's dependence on place. Meanings and belongings of a place are the signs of the place which are perceived as inseparably associated and the lack of which would weaken the identity and history of the place. On the other hand, the knowledge of the symbols and signs existing in a place, the dominant culture of the place, and collective memories promote place identity and history so that the individual's awareness of the place is improved and they can establish a deep connection with the place. The physical appearance, activities, and the significance of the raw material constitute the identity of a place (Afroogh, 1998).

Proshansky et al (1978) took the initiative in examining the relations between city and character and proposed the theory of place identity. Based on this theory, experienced spaces include a portion of place

identity. Place identity constitutes a portion of the individual identity of a human being and is the result of one's general knowledge of the physical world; this knowledge includes the memories, ideas, feelings, attitudes, values, preferences, concepts, and the behavioral and experiential ideals of an individual in relation with the complex and diverse physical environments which constitute the experiential space of human including one's conceptions and behaviors.

On the other hand, this should be considered that identity has origins in place and time, that is, the identity of a place can be affected by different factors at different times as the spatial conception of the observer changes in the course of time; one's conception of an urban space is different at different historical phases. This depends on the socio-cultural lifestyle of the individual and space function at different times. The issue of time calculation in designing was first tackled by Lynch. He postulates the necessity of the relationship of the place which is currently being created and the not-too-far past and close future and states that we organize our experience in time and place (Lynch, 1981; Tavasoli, pp. 18-19). In addition, identity factors change as a function of the place and geography, that is, the factors creating the identity of a place are different from those of another, thereby distinguishing a place from another and giving them their own specific identities.

Also, creating the identity of a place requires an awareness of the determinant factors involved. Accordingly, drawing on the opinions of major theoreticians of the area including Proshansky 1978, Massey 1944, Relph 1979, Landry 2000, Lang 1994, Jacobs 1961, Lynch 1981, Wagner 1890, Schulz 1975, Alexander 1981, and Cullen 1961 the factors are presented in the comparative table below.

Therefore, the major factors influencing the place identity of the citizens: Preserving the memorializing elements of the place, designing for the creation of strong links between the individual and the place create the sense of belonging and promote collective identity and the sense of anthropophilia, the lack of each can weaken place identity.

Table 1. Documentation of place identity factors

		Criteria and Factors															
Place Identity	activity	individual identity	favorable mental image	space	time	availability	meaning	Liveliness	memories	social content	cultural content	The external-internal perception of individual	Human	Place	Legibility	Variety	Peace
Theoreticians																	
Doreen Massey,1944				■						■							
Relph,1979		■										■					
Landry,2000																■	
Lang,1994					■												
Jacobs , 1961	■							■								■	
Kevin Lynch1972			■					■									
Otto Wagner1890	■												■				
Norberg-Schulz1975			■					■			■			■			
Alexander,1981			■									■					
Gorden Cullen1961									■							■	

Square in Islamic cities

As an urban space having more destination activities and less passing ones, square has common notable features like wideness that depends proportionally on number of cross route, having special functions constantly or during specific times, and existence probability of physical elements at its center (Soltanzadeh, 2006, p. 82). The features of square depicted differently in different cultures in different periods. In Iranian culture, square was a (regular or irregular dimensioned) space performing as a place for activities and its name choice showed its main activity (NagiZadeh, 2006). Concerning the meaning of urban square (also known as Maydan or Meydanin Persian), Dehkhoda encyclopedia contains: "a wide space around which houses and shops are located", and adds that this word is originally Persian. There is "Plaza" in English, "Piatzza" in Italian, and "Praça" in

Spanish, all derived from Latin "Plati" corresponding urban square. Plaza is defined as an open urban public space which is paved mostly with hard materials, to which entering of automobile is forbidden, and mainly there is a space for waking, sitting, relaxing, eating and drinking, and looking at near views. Tavassoli and Bonyadi introduce urban square a space performing the role of combining houses, urban elements, and valley elements (Pakzad, 2006). Pakzad mentions squares as one of most influential urban spaces on citizens' minds, as for as he mentions that usually the realization of different urban regions and the simplest way of giving address to any stranger is guiding him using squares as the urban indexes. In his viewpoint, stillness, aggregation, and integration can be mentioned as significant features of urban knots, which can be created using some strategies.

Purpose	Strategy
Stillness	Persuading halt and non-motion behaviors through persuading of passers to decrease motion pace, decreasing passing-walking-traffic, and increasing destination traffic
	-Providing relaxing facilitation through existence of different areas for motion and stillness -Creating peace of mind in citizens through predictability of events in the space, predictability of space's framework, and creating supervision possibility of the space -Facilitating social contacts through facilitating ease of presence in the space, presence of different social groups, and easy seeing and being seen

	-Opportunity to perceive the space through perception of the whole space and its details
	-Communicating between human and the space through freedom of human activity in the space and possibility of manipulation of the space by the citizens
Aggregation	-Possibility of gathering of citizens through existence of required space for gathering and ease of presence in the space for the citizens
	-Absorbing different activities through having appropriate base for different activities, and possibility of getting involved in different activities for different people
	-Emphasizing on being center through gathering, human groups, and essential factors
	-Sense of belonging to the collection through possibility of individual's activity beside other social groups, association of individual with others in activities
	-Persuading to halt through persuasion of decreasing pace, persuasion of non-motion activities, and transforming passing traffic to destination traffic
Integration	-Integrity in physical elements through integration of body and pavement
	-Spatial integrity through lack of certain separation of spatial regions
	-Activity integrity through minimizing spatial separation and creating soft borders between activity regions
	-Possibility of crating mental picture of the whole space through perception of the whole of the space together and the relation of whole-part

Table 2: Purposes, strategies and policies of planning and designing of urban knots and how to supply them (Source: Pakzad, 2006)

Studied Area (introduce studied area)

According to the authorized divisions of Tehran, Baharestan Square is located in the 12th region of Tehran municipality (Figs. 1). The square has an outstanding position and includes valuable constructions and physical elements which have the capacity to recreate the identity of the place. It is currently surrounded by fifty stores providing different type of goods and services.

One of the most important places established during the Constitutionalist Revolution and is still considered prominent is the National Parliament

building and its adjoining square, Baharestan. The square has undergone changes many times but due to the existence of the parliament building has remained the main place for social and political gatherings. Baharestan Square was selected as our case for the present study after considering the existing theoretical background in selecting the major factors affecting the identity of place. This section the reasons behind selecting the site are extensively discussed. To this purpose, the factors and criteria are determined through the place identification process, thereby developing a general framework for recreating place identity in Iranian-Islamic squares.

Fig 1: Position of Baharestan Square in its urban fabric. Tehran-Iran (National Cartographic Center)

Due to the location of the parliament building in Baharestan Garden, the square still remained as a central context for political activities in Iran. The building of Masoodie, Negarestan Garden, Sepahsalar Mosque, Parliament building, the old library of Sepahsalar, the building of the Ministry of Culture, the Center for Persian Language and Literature, and even the musical instrument stores surrounding the square are amongst the valuable uses and constructions of the square. The square has gone completely unnoticed whereas it has history as old as

the history of the political events of Iran and is one of the most significant squares of the country.

After determining the historical features of the square, the factors affecting the identity of a place have to be specified; place identification process is used for this objective. The place identification follows the process (Rafi'izadeh, 2005:11):

- In the early stages of place identification, its existence is known; then as the process proceeds further and gets more complex, its

features and characteristics gain more significance. In other words, with the development of identification, the characteristics exceed the character in importance.

- There should be a connection between the users and the identity of the place to minimize the difference between the real identity of the place and the identity assumed by the users, and the agreed upon identity is the same as the assumed identity.

Accordingly, in the first step the current features of the square are presented in the table3 (SWOT); then, the factors will be ranked based on the data collected from the users of the space.

Data analyzed

According to research method, this research is quantitative – qualitative. So at first was analyzed by SWOT technique. The table (3) is the result of the survey and documentary investigations on the position of this place.

Table 3. Major Factors affecting the recreating of the identity of Baharestan Square

Weakness and Threats	Strengthen and Opportunities
The gap created in the wall by numerous streets and the gap in the eastern side of the square due to the lack of visual quality of the fences.	Land use variety, compatible land uses (e.g., handicrafts, photography, and other minor services), the pedestrian-orientedness of the square, which promotes the identity of it and encourages the presence of diverse social groups, the social spaces left from the past, and the valuable historical buildings, bodies and complexes.
The low (two storied) on the western side.	The presence of the old parliament and some other old constructions on the southern side of the square, as urban symbols, and some northern walls of the square as valuable works.
The presence of empty plaques or independent buildings, and, thus, the lack of wall on the edges of the square	
Problematic land uses (workshops, printing centers, depositories) and the heavy traffic in the square	The presence of the symbolic and evocative elements like the parliament, school and the major mosque of Ostad Motahari
The lack of regulations for the density of development of tall buildings	The capacity to attract the public.
	Favorable environment and climate

Descriptive data

The descriptive analysis of the data shows that 76.7 percent of the respondents were male and 23.3 percent were female. The larger number of male respondents is because the uses in the square are conducted by men. %60 of the participants ranged in age from 25-35, the least number of participants were

51-99 years old, and 43 participants were 36-50 years old.

Concerning the socio-educational background of the participants, the larger portion of the sample (i.e. %46.9) had Diploma, and the smallest portion had MA/Msc or PhD. The majority of the participants

(%58.3) was employed and had stable jobs while the others (i.e. %41.7) were unemployed. Most of the participants had shops near the square and their presence in the square were due to their occupational dependence rather the square's sense of inviting or for recreational purposes.

Inferential data (Statistic)

Based on the hypotheses stated in the manuscript, the criteria extracted from the relevant literature, and the available historical texts and documents, a questionnaire was developed to elicit the criteria required to be met for the purpose of recreating the identity of Baharestan Square. The questionnaire was administered to a sample of 180 residents of Tehran. Using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences software (SPSS version17) the collected data were

analyzed in order to test the stated hypotheses, which sought to explore

The relationships between the elements and factors affecting the identity of the place. At this stage, correlation analyses were run in order to test the hypotheses and to do exploratory analysis on the relationships between the dependent and independents variables involved. Before testing the hypotheses via correlation analyses, two general questions concerning the priority of the factors affecting the presence of people in the square and the priority of the factors affecting the sense of belonging to space, were to be answered. The results showed that about %50 of the residents considered the historical factors of the square to be the major factors. In addition, the history of the square was the most determinant factor affecting the sense of belonging to the place.

Table 4.The two most important factors affecting the presence of people in Baharestan Square

Background	Factor	Frequency	Percent
Presence in Space	The history of the square	47.8	5.5
	appearance of the square	23.5	24
Place attachment	The history of the square	45	49
	Activities in the square	24.5	27

Table 5.Results of Hypothesis test

Hypothesis	Variable	Sub-criteria	Test	significance	Test result	P value
First hypothesis	Historical Structural	Historical potential of square	Gamma	0.000	✓	32.47
		Valuable historical walls	Gamma	0.000	✓	14.73
Second hypothesis	Scio-cultural	Effects on stranger's behavior	Gamma	0.034	✓	13.62
		Sense of comfort	Gamma	0.014	✓	15.90
		Sense of fear	Gamma	0.440	✓	5.81
		sense of inviting	Gamma	0.000	✓	27.33
		Sense of democracy	Gamma	0.034	✓	17.53
Third hypothesis	Structural-functional	Parliament building	Gamma	0.000	✓	63.10
		Sepahsalar Complex	Gamma	0/027	✓	42.57
		Negarestan garden	Gamma	0.000	✓	28.49
		Masoodie complex	Gamma	0.006	✓	12.03
		Physical and functional quality	Gamma	0.044	✓	13.92
Fourth hypothesis	Historical political	Shelling of the parliament	Gamma	0/027	✓	14. 27
		The history of constitutionalism	Gamma	0.000	✓	32.10

- HYPOTHESIS 1**
As shown in Table 5, there is a weak relationship (0.25) but significant ($p = 0.05$) between the place identity and the status of Baharestan Square. This means that the place identity of the square goes hand in hand with its historical value.
- HYPOTHESIS 2**
Table 5 shows that there is a significant and positive correlation between all the subcomponents of the socio-cultural variable and place identity. This means that increase in place identity results in the reinforcement of the sense of inviting. Amongst all the subcomponents, the sense of inviting, democracy, and composure are, respectively, the most important factors affecting the recreating of the identity of Baharestan Square.
- HYPOTHESIS 3**
The results of the correlation analyses showed that all the valuable structural elements affect the place identity of the square. The building of the parliament was rated the most important structural element and Sepahsalar Garden and

Negarestan Garden were ranked the second and the third most important elements, respectively.

- HYPOTHESIS 4**
A significant and positive correlation was found between all the subcomponents of the historical-political variable on one side and place identity on the other. The subcomponent the history of constitutionalism was ranked higher than the shelling of the parliament in terms of impact on the identity of the square.

Discussion and Proposed Conceptual Framework

Based on the correlation analysis of the data, the most important factors affecting the identity of Baharestan Square were determined. Hence the significance level was set to .05, the findings can be generalized. In this section some policies and strategies for the promotion of place identity in the historical squares of Iran are proposed. In order to have objective representations, the strategies are developed in structural-functional forms although the development of socio-cultural strategies is necessary due to the non-structural dimensions of identity.

Table 6. Design's policies and strategies

Variable	Strategy	Policy
Structural-Functional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting the physical quality of the square Increasing the sense of enclosure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adding variety to physical details Creating rhythm and harmony in developing the bodies Reconstructing the architectural styles of Qajari and Pahlavi Controlling and minimizing bothering elements The consistency of the morphologic appearance of the bodies Following the window patterns of the adjoining buildings Creating 1-meter high places around the square.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highlighting historical elements Creating signs and symbols relating to the historical events Variety in uses Promoting physical elements Communicating the identity of the square 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the Parliament building, Masoodie complex Negarestan Garden, Sepahsalar complex, the Statue of Modarres Creating statues relating to the identity of the square Rehabilitating elements which communicate a sense of identity (Laghante Café) Creating visual and physical connections between the spaces and important signs and factors Orienting all the elements in the square towards the Parliament building
Socio-Cultural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting social interactions Promoting the sense of inviting Variety along the area Communicating the identity of the square Designing the pavement of the square 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimizing the connection between pedestrians and cars Stopping the traffic Avoiding level discrepancy, and the breaking of pavement Providing spaces for seating, pausing and watching Adding variety to the land uses Removing visual barriers in the sidewalk Preserving and promoting evocative elements Paving with emphasis upon prominent locations. Avoiding the use of construction materials like asphalt and concrete.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Facilitating the presence of people in large numbers · Creating a democratic space · Promoting social participation · Promoting place identity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Developing high quality seating space with urban furniture · Highlighting historical elements which can link the present to the past · Variety in land uses, which appeal to a wide range of tastes · Providing water, green space and lighting systems · Providing enough walking space · Using designing amenities
---	---

Variety of elements could make strong sense of place identity based on the socio-cultural and socio-political driving forces. Social, cultural and political events that accure in places in associated with symbolical signs make collective memory for a nation. In the case of Baharestan square several factors affected it, place identity which we discovered in this research including sense of inviting, democracy, composure and structural

elements. Also, it is concluded that there is direct correlation between historic-political variable and place identity in the Baharestan case. So, it could be inferred that there are every necessary means in order to promote the square identity and it depends on the in charging institute and organization such as Tehran municipality. Figure 2 shows conceptual framework of Major factors in recreating the place identity of the historical Baharestan Square

Fig2: conceptual framework

Conclusion

Place identity concerns the observable characteristics which make the place identifiable. The identity of a place is reminiscent of the past events related to that place and makes a strong association between the present and the past. Due to the lack of connection between the present and past of the socio-cultural features, the trend of changes occurred ever since the beginning of modernization has resulted in identity gap rather than continuity. If there is going to be a change in an urban space, it should be done in way that brings back some memories of the past to the people. Drastic changes in urban space can erase all the memories which are parts of the history and the life of the people living in that space. In the present study, place identity in one of the most evocative and important square of Tehran, Baharestan Square, was investigated. The present study was an attempt to draw a general picture of the issue under discussion. The results of the survey examination of the opinions of different groups of people showed that highlighting the Parliament building as the most important national element of the square rehabilitating and reconstructing old constructions, establishing activities and uses relating to the identity of the place, creating sign and symbols contributing to the identity of the square, creating a democratic space, a proper mental image, facilitating the gathering of people in large numbers are assumed to contribute to the identity of Baharestan Square. The most important factors in recreating the identity of the square include, which can be generalized to other squares are presented in Fig.2.

References

- 1) Afrough, E. Space and Social Inequality: A Model for Spatial Separation and its Consequences. Unpublished Thesis. Tehran: Tarbiat Modares University.1998.
- 2) Aniel R. Williams and Joseph W. Roggen buck, Measuring Place Attachment: Some Preliminary Results, Paper Presented at the Session on Outdoor Planning and Management NRPA Symposium on Leisure Research San Antonio, Department of Forestry Virginia, Polytechnic Institute & State University, Blacksburg, Virginia 24061-0324, 703-231-4031, Texas, October 20-22, (1989).
- 3) Belinda Yuen, Searching for place identity in Singapore, Department of Real Estate, School of Design and Environment, The National University of Singapore,4 Architecture Drive, Singapore, , Habitat International 29: 197-214 (2005).
- 4) Davenport, M.A., & Anderson, D. H. (2005). Getting from sense of place to place-based management: An interpretive investigation of place meanings and perception of landscape change. *Society and Natural Resource*, 18, 625-641
- 5) Habibi. M. From Shar to City. Tehran. Tehran University. 2003.
- 6) Lynne C. Manzo, *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 25 (2005) 67-86, For better or worse: Exploring multiple dimensions of place meaning, Department of Landscape Architecture, College of Architecture and Urban Planning, University of Washington, Seattle, WA 98195, USA, Available online March 2005.
- 7) NagiZadeh, M. (2006). Reflections on the process of reform in Iranian Cities. *Journal of Fine Arts* .
- 8) Pakzad. J. Square and Urban Space. *Shahrdariha Magazine*. Appendix 67: 15-16 (2004).
- 9) Pakzad, J. (2006). Guide for urban space design in Iran. the Ministry of Housing and Urban Planning, Department of Urban Planning and Architecture.
- 10) Proshansky, H.M. 'The city and self-identity', *Journal of Environment and Behaviour*, Vol. 10: 57-83 (1978).
- 11) Proshansky, H.M., Fabian, A.K. and Kaminoff, R. 'Place-identity: Physical world socialization of the self', *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, Vol. 3: 57-83 (1983).
- 12) Rafi'izadeh, N, *The Social-Spatial Process of Place Identity. An Introduction to Understanding and Reinforcement of the Iranian City*. Abadi Magazine 48, (2005).
- 13) Relph, E. *Place and place lessness* London: Pion, 1976.
- 14) Soltanzadeh, H. (2006). urban spaces in the historical context of Iran. Tehran: the Office of Cultural Research.
- 15) Sumartojo S. 2012, *The Fourth Plinth: creating and contesting national identity in Trafalgar Square, 2005 -2010*, *Journal of Cultural Geographies*, Sage.
- 16) Shafik. S, Aly, A, 2011, *Modernization and regionalism: Approaches for sustainable, revival of local urban identity*, *Procedia Engineering*, No 21.
- 17) Tavasoli, M *The Structure of City and Architecture in the Dry and Warm Climate of Iran*. Tehran: Tehran University.1996.
- 18) Tavasoli, M., &Bonyadi, N. *Urban Space Development (2)*. The Iranian Centre for the Urbanization and Architecture Studies.1993.
- 19) Webster dictionary, 1988.